

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D3.7 – Case study coordination guidelines – update M26

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is an update of D3.3 “Case-study coordination guidelines” which presented basic guidelines and recommendations for case studies to follow to improve coordination across all cases. This deliverable presents an overall view of the coordination carried out across all cases and a global analysis of the requirements established for all cases, considering the ongoing empirical research for the work being developed in case studies.

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1 Introduction

The current deliverable is an update of the core guidelines, recommendations, and requirements for the coordination and field research being conducted across all case studies, following the research design and methodological guidelines established in D3.6 “Multi-site research design and methodological framework – update M26”. The final case-study description may be found in D3.5 “Case-study selection - update M24” and as stated before, research conducted in WP4-7 allows to establish the overall in-depth context in which each case study is nested, through the Socio-Ecological System Framework validated in D3.4 “Case-studies comparative report - part 1”.

As stated before, the intent of the provided guidelines was to enable stakeholders of each case to conduct their research in a manner that makes sense to the opportunities and limitations of the communities that are being researched, while still producing broader awareness and coordination of the successes and challenges that each case may be having over time. Such coordination is intended to assist before, during, and at the completion of each case’s research study. Coordinating case-studies that include different levels of scale and context may become a challenge if not governed properly.

Hence, this deliverable presents an overall view of the coordination carried out across all cases and a global analysis of the requirements established for all cases. Thus, the main goal of the current deliverable is to present each case-studies’ qualitative research quality assurance evaluated by COREQ’s domains 1 and 2, pertaining interviews conducted between June 2022 and February 2023. Domain 3 will be contemplated upon case-studies primary-data analysis in D3.8 “Case-study final comparative report – update M34”.

Ultimately, the coordination, guidelines, recommendations, and requirements shall improve COVINFORM’s ability to generate a more comprehensive perspective of communities’ resilience that can be applied on future crisis situations, and together with other work being developed in COVINFORM will later provide input for recommendations in WP8.

2 Global Analysis of Baseline Requirements

Providing greater transparency and generalizability of the inputs and outputs of all case-studies through these coordination guidelines, recommendations, and requirements, amplifies the impact that each individual case may have upon science and society, as well as allows for a common platform of understanding and scientific advancement. As stated before, rather than merely an after-action component where results are tallied at the conclusion of various studies, case study coordination is a process that occurs before, during, and after a study is engaged and completed (see Appendix A).

Moreover, various criteria for coordinating basic and applied research may be utilised across different fields of expertise, and various data reporting mechanisms may improve comparison of case study inputs and data across a range of disciplines and practices. Thus, a set of core issues were addressed in case-study research, through meetings/consortiums, presentations, and other WP3 deliverable tasks (see Table 1).

Table 1. Core Issues Addressed in Case-study Research.

Core Issues Addressed in Case-study Research
1. What purpose does the hypothesis, thesis, research questions, and research approach serve? To generate new knowledge and theory, to view individual and/or collective opinion on an event, or to test existing theory? How do these contribute to COVINFORM goals? What are the potential impacts of the research?
2. What are the common and complimentary research questions and/or variables addressed by different case-studies focusing on similar target populations? What kind of methods will be used by the case-study considering qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-methods approaches? How does the choice of these methods across case-studies support comparability and complementarity?
3. How will the research team put the case-study in practice to address the research questions? What limitations may be faced within the information gathering process?
4. How can we ensure the internal and external validity case studies and their output? There is a need to ensure comparability and generalizability of findings, while also acknowledging the unique socioeconomic, socioenvironmental, and socio-political contexts by which the interviewed populations operate within.

With respect to mixed-methods research, the COnsolidated criteria for REporting Qualitative research (COREQ) checklist (see Appendix B for the table template) is one tool available to not only improve the coordination and communication of research studies, but also to improve their internal and external validity by identifying unique/ungeneralizable factors within the study as well as potential biases or limitations within the dataset (Tong et al., 2007; Dossett et al., 2021). As explained in more detail in D3.3, the COREQ checklist is divided into three domains:

- 1. Note the role of the researcher upon and within the research question and environment (see section 2.1.1);
- 2. Address concerns of study design to note potential flaws within the interview process and help strengthen such areas of potential weakness (see section 2.2.1);
- 3. Offer suggestions for interview analysis and facilitate the ability to transform qualitative information derived from interviews and focus groups into useful information pertinent to the given research question, including quantifiable statistical analyses (to be included in depth in D3.8 – see section 2.3 for brief explanation at the end).

Overall, the COREQ checklist can be a helpful launch point for practitioners by helping them address potential concerns before, during, and after research, as well as by providing a systematic framework of research it also provides a reliable background for the future development of comparable case-studies.

The ongoing coordination allows the project and its partners to benefit from their hard work and develop a common set of findings and discussion points for the benefit of science and policymaking.

This section will present how the baseline requirements regarding inputs (also see Table 2), outputs (also see Table 3), and logistics/administration established (also see Table 4) in D3.3 “Case-study coordination guidelines” were, are being, and will continue to be secured throughout all the process and work being developed in WP3, as well as a global analysis of the tool established to assess qualitative research quality based on partners’ work carried out in WP3 research.

2.1 Coordination Guidelines: Inputs

Generalizability in scientific research refers to the extent to which the findings of a study can be applied to other populations, settings, and contexts beyond the specific sample and conditions of the study. In other words, it refers to the extent to which the results can be generalized beyond the specific study sample. Inevitably, this requires rigorous controls regarding how input data/information is identified, collected, and synthesized. In quantitative research, generalizability is often achieved through random sampling and large sample sizes, which increase the chances that the sample is representative of the population being studied. In qualitative research, generalizability is more challenging to achieve, but can be enhanced by using theoretical frameworks, triangulation, member checking, and other methods (Carminati, 2018).

To achieve generalizability, data inputs must be gathered or analysed through one or more strategies or methods, including examples such as:

- Using a large sample size: A large sample size increases the chances that the findings will be representative of the population being studied.
- Triangulation: Using multiple methods of data collection and analysis increases the validity of the findings.
- Member checking: Involving the participants in the interpretation of the data helps ensure that the findings accurately reflect their perspectives.
- Peer review: Having other researchers review the study design and findings increases the credibility of the study.
- Using a theoretical framework: Using a theoretical framework to guide the study helps ensure that the findings are relevant and generalizable to the broader literature on the topic.
- Using a rigorous data analysis: Using rigorous data analysis techniques such as thematic analysis, discourse analysis, and grounded theory can help ensure the findings are generalizable
- Reporting the findings in detail: Reporting the findings in a detailed and transparent manner can help other researchers understand the context and limitations of the study, and therefore assess the generalizability of the findings.

Ensuring generalizability in qualitative research, specifically in interview studies, can be a challenging task. However, there are several ways in which the generalizability of the findings can be enhanced. One way is to use a theoretical framework to guide the study. This helps ensure that the findings are relevant and generalizable to the broader literature on the topic. Additionally, using a diverse sample that represents different perspectives and backgrounds can help ensure that the findings are generalizable to a larger population. Using a purposive sampling strategy, such as criterion-based sampling, snowball sampling, or theoretical sampling, can also help select participants that are most likely to provide information relevant to the research question. A large sample size can also increase the chances that the findings will be representative of the population being studied.

For COVINFORM, the COREQ Requirements ensure generalizability via interview studies by utilising:

- 1. A theoretical framework to guide study analysis:

COVINFORM grounds all cases in syndemic theory, which drives all COREQ answers. This is a framework that explains how different forms of social and health problems interact and exacerbate each other, leading to worse outcomes than would occur if each problem were considered in isolation. The term “syndemic” is a combination of the words “synergy” and “epidemic” and refers to the idea that multiple health and social problems interact in ways that are additive or multiplicative, leading to worse outcomes than would occur if each problem were considered in isolation. For example, a person living in poverty may also have poor access to healthcare, which can lead to poor mental health and an increased likelihood of substance abuse. This in turn can lead to a cycle of poverty, poor health, and social disadvantage.

- 2. Criterion-based purposeful sampling strategies:

All COVINFORM cases utilize criterion-based purposeful sampling, where participants are selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria are the characteristics or attributes that participants must possess in order to be eligible for the study, while the exclusion criteria are characteristics or attributes that make participants ineligible for the study. Criterion-based purposeful sampling is a flexible technique that allows researchers to target specific groups of people who are likely to have relevant experiences or perspectives on the research topic (in this case, community disruption via COVID). It is particularly useful when the research question is focused on a specific population or group, and when the sample size is small. And, critically, the criteria help indicate what is unique and likely non-generalizable (e.g., the context-dependent experiences of a specific group in a specific city), and which are more likely so (e.g., the effect of having less socioeconomic status during COVID disruption). COREQ helps shape criterion-based purposeful sampling through its battery of questions.

- 3. Triangulating qualitative interviews with other available sources to aid in the deduction of themes regarding community perspectives of COVID disruption (specifically, whether specific communities experience disproportionate levels of disruption at various stages of the pandemic relative to the general population of their local city or country):

COVINFORM case studies mix rich narratives and themes derived via interviews alongside other pertinent quantitative and semi-qualitative information deduced from other COVINFORM tasks.

Triangulation in criterion-based purposeful sampling for interview research refers to the use of multiple methods and sources of data to increase the validity of the findings. Triangulation can be used to check the consistency and accuracy of the data, and to identify any discrepancies or biases in the findings. For many case studies, multiple qualitative sources are consulted – interviews, surveys, and document analysis, among others. Likewise, the use of other elements of COVINFORM, such as socioeconomic trend analysis, can provide additional datapoints that confirm or question interview narratives. Using triangulation in criterion-based purposeful sampling for interview research can help increase the validity of the findings by providing multiple perspectives on the research question, and by identifying any discrepancies or biases in the data. It can also help increase the generalizability of the findings by providing a more comprehensive view of the research question.

Table 2. Case-studies baseline requirements: Inputs.

Generalizability of Inputs: Identifying, collecting, and synthesizing core data requirements		
A. Each case shall be coordinated based upon the inputs (research questions, hypotheses, and qualitative/quantitative data).		
A1. Cases must be clearly framed, explicitly defining, and bounding the case/group being studied based upon their socio-ecological and socioeconomic systems.		
A1a. Should include the selection of units of analysis that are comparable, where possible (e.g., geographical scale, focus on vulnerability/disproportionate impacts faced by some groups in society, and focus on the COVINFORM cross-cutting issues (domains of government, public health, community and citizens responses, communication, and information)		
Since the COVINFORM project intends to provide benefits to practitioners, decision-makers, and the scientific community, proper coordination allows us to develop a common framing and communication strategy to understand the commonalities across individual cases and speak with a shared and scientifically-grounded voice in characterizing the socio-ecological and socioeconomic systems.		
A2. Multiple data sources should be considered.		
A2a. Primary data (gathered either to describe the systems - government, public health, community, and communication/ information research -, or focusing on the Research Questions and analysis of the specific case study)	A2b. Secondary data that contributes to systems description, contextualize case-studies, or ensuring broader comparability (within COVINFORM case-studies or with research developed in other communities or including different geographical levels of analysis)	A2c. All input data are coded and described in a simple, concise, and jargon-free manner to maximize understanding and promote transparency amongst COVINFORM team members.
A3. Change over time is a critical variable of analysis.		
Considerations of time are critical as the conditions of a case may change over time. For example, considering COVID-19 impacts, target populations may have been affected differently at different stages or waves of the pandemic, hence adaptive responses may also have been different. Tracking how our units of analysis change (or do not change) over time provides a far richer and more complete narrative to understand different behaviours and operations during and after the pandemic		

2.2 Global analysis of COREQ checklist across case-studies: Domain 1

This subsection provides a global analysis of the qualitative research quality regarding *input guidelines*. See Appendix C1 for the complete COREQ information of Domain 1 provided by each case-study. Subsection 2.2.1 provides a global analysis of the qualitative research quality regarding *output guidelines*, where Domain 2 will be addressed.

COREQ Domain 1: Research Team

Domain 1 of the COREQ Requirements involves the evaluation of the investigatory team that will conduct qualitative research. What are their credentials and background? What is their experience and training with qualitative methods? What is their relationship with the subjects to be interviewed? These and other questions help identify potential interviewer biases, possible conflicts or skew in interview data based upon prior relationships with the target community, and other potential errors in study design (and, in turn, to correct revealed issues to promote the robustness of qualitative interview output).

The first subcategory of COREQ Domain 1 focuses on the personal characteristics of the interviewing team. Most case studies included in D3.7 primarily utilized a single interviewer, while others operated in teams of two, three, or more. All interviewees possessed familiarity with qualitative methods, with most having direct experience interviewing minority and/or marginalized communities in prior projects. Most participants hold academic appointments, where qualitative research training is offered, and rigorous evaluation standards (e.g., Institutional Review Boards and external Ethical Review Authorities) oversee and approve human subjects research studies. Most of the case studies were solely or primarily conducted by women-identifying interviewers. Experiences of interviewers varied, ranging from extensive qualitative field research in a Malawi refugee camp (UANTWERPEN), to the regular education of undergraduate and graduate students on qualitative methods in the interviewer's day job at university. Likewise, while all cases were conducted by experienced interviewers, their disciplinary basis for such training varied widely: including journalism (UK_MDI; UGOT), to Human Geography (Swansea), to anthropology (SYNYO), and others. Some teams utilizing multiple interviewers, such as SYNYO, utilized researchers with different disciplinary backgrounds (anthropology, communications, etc). Ultimately, the cases were relatively similar in some personal characteristics of the interviewees (e.g., majority women interviewers, significant credentials in administering qualitative interviews, etc). Some differences, including the number of interviewers on a team (one versus many) as well as disciplinary experience (how they were trained in qualitative methods) should be considered when evaluating case feedback. Moreover, it should be noted that language limitations are a barrier when interviewing respondents with migrant background (e.g., in Sweden it was only used Swedish and English since there were not resources for interpreters).

The second subcategory of COREQ Domain 1 focuses on the relationship and familiarity, if any that the research teams held with participants (and vice versa). Some of the case teams established relationships with study participants prior to the study (e.g., SYNYO with prior projects in supermarket outreach; Swansea noting brief contact with nurses and healthcare managers prior to study execution). Others, like UGOT and UANTWERPEN, did not have prior relationships. With respect to the information made available by interviewees to participants, responses were generally formal – the interviewer's affiliation and credentials, as well as the source of their funding via COVINFORM. Given the vulnerability of many case study populations sought for interview through D.3.7, accounting for prior familiarity with these communities, as well as the language used to explain the purpose of the study,

is essential to anticipate possible trust or mistrust of the community to the researcher’s aims. Given that the research teams have familiarity with their target participant populations and are able to describe their purpose (impact of COVID upon the minority community) in a clear and consistent way, no significant limitations are likely to arise.

2.3 Coordination Guidelines: Outputs

As noted in Section 2.1, outcome comparability and generalizability is a core goal of the COVINFORM project – what are the common themes or experiences of minority communities throughout COVID, and in what ways did these communities experience disproportionate disruption relative to the general population? COREQ’s reporting guidelines for input generalizability help ensure comparability of outcomes, including discussion based upon sample characteristics (size, age, gender, and other relevant characteristics - this allows other researchers to assess the representativeness of the sample, and to assess the generalizability of the findings), and methods used to analyse data (the data analysis techniques used, including the software used, the coding scheme, and the steps taken to ensure the reliability and validity of the data analysis). Specific common coding themes via syndemic theory include how communities experienced economic, sociocultural, infrastructural, or governmental (e.g., access to government communications about COVID, as well as financial programs intended to alleviate COVID disruption through society).

Table 3. Case-studies baseline requirements: Outputs.

Generalizability of conclusions, that is interpretation and deduction of conclusions from case data
<p>B. Each case shall be coordinated based upon the inputs (research questions, hypotheses, and qualitative/quantitative data).</p>
<p>As noted in Section 2.1, COREQ facilitates input data generalizability by ensuring that (a) the collected data do not possess hidden biases, and (b) that the interviewee qualifications are well framed and driven by common theory, methods, and analysis practices. COVINFORM utilizes criterion-based purposeful sampling, syndemic theory, and triangulation to ensure that input materials are comparable (acknowledging that some elements of each case study are contextually unique).</p>
<p>B1. Principal investigators of each case shall share their research findings regularly, suggesting correlations and even causal linkages between system disruption and response/recovery.</p>
<p>COVINFORM held regular meetings to coordinate research motivations, methods, and analysis via a standardized format. Our intention was not to limit the scope or abilities of any individual case team, but rather to ground all investigators in syndemic theory, understand the limitations of the study, and promote triangulation with other case studies as well as quantitative data from other tasks in COVINFORM.</p>
<p>B2. Output sharing shall emphasize two core factors:</p> <p>a) factors the investigator believes is unique to their case or population under study;</p> <p>b) potentially generalizable conclusions.</p>
<p>As a safeguard to external validity, all output assessment shall include an understanding of the socio-ecological and socioeconomic systems that comprise the incentives, behaviours, and pandemic response/recovery strategies within the case.</p>

2.4 Global analysis of COREQ checklist across case-studies: Domain 2

This subsection provides a global analysis of the qualitative research quality regarding *output guidelines*. See Appendix C2 for the complete COREQ information of Domain 2 provided by each case-study.

COREQ Domain 2: Internal and External Validity

Where COREQ Domain 1 set the stage by addressing interviewer qualifications and potential heuristics/biases in relation to qualitative study of the target population, Domain 2 unpacks the study design – specifically, how can we ensure internal and external validity of the study? Core questions include:

- the methodological or theoretical orientation the study designers use and test
- the strategy to select participants, and identify potential shortcomings or validity concerns related to study dropouts
- the setting and conditions by which the qualitative study was conducted
- the data collection strategy before, during, and after the interview process.

The first subcategory of COREQ Domain 2 focuses on the theoretical framework utilized by the research teams to conduct their qualitative interviews. The common grounding theory of all cases was complex systems and intersectionality – evaluating how the intricate interactions between social, economic, governmental, and health systems influence population experience amidst COVID, with added stresses likely experienced by minority or disenfranchised communities. Beyond this common theoretical base, perspectives varied widely across the cases. Examples include embodiment (the embodied experience of risk – SYNNO), social constructivism and sensemaking (UGOT), Ethnographic complex systems analysis (MDI), and phenomenology. These diverging perspectives will have some differences in the type of discussion and analysis that can be drawn from interview output and raw data, though will afford a richer narrative base to address questions related to how various communities were affected by COVID disruption (through the lens of complex systems).

The second subcategory of COREQ Domain 2 focuses on how participants were selected for survey or interview. While interviews and surveys were used across the cases in equivalent numbers, all tended to rely upon purposeful (colloquially, ‘snowball sampling’) to identify potential participants in public settings. The intention here was largely to seek engagement in a face-to-face interaction – gaining participant interest in public spaces that they were already inhabiting (notably, some cases such as MDI noted a use of telephone and email engagement rather than face-to-face). After initial engagement, follow-up was often conducted through telephone or email. Sample sizes varied, with those studies conducting interviews reaching at least ten participants (with some having far more, like MDI with 31, or KEMEA with five groups of separate interviewees of minimum five in population). Many cases did not comment on the dropout rate of their studies – some indicated that tracking dropouts would be scientifically difficult to estimate given the opportunistic sampling style of public engagement. Those studies conducting digital surveys were able to track their dropout rates. Overall, a key challenge for all cases will be to ensure the external validity of their sampled participants – ensuring that their participant population is sufficiently narrowly defined to prevent sampling error and an unrealistic set of interview feedback that is not representative of a broader target population. Another challenge pertains to the fact that respondents who chose to participate might diverge from the population in terms of representativeness (e.g., those who chose to and are more willing to

participate might be more integrated). However, we are interested in the experiences and narratives of these populations. If anything, we can speculate that those who we cannot reach might live in harsher conditions and be even more hindered by the COVID-19 pandemic impacts.

The third subcategory of COREQ Domain 2 involves the setting of where data was collected, and the conditions that data was collected in. As noted above, most engagements were face-to-face, although most had digital follow-up. Non-participants are noted as present in several cases due to the public nature of the study (UANTWERPEN, UGOT), while other cases did not respond to the non-participant inquiry (one case, MDI, noted that no non-participants were present in their interviews). All cases defined their target population and subsequent interview samples using language of gender (e.g., women working in supermarkets – SYNNO), migrants or migrant background (UGOT; UANTWERPEN), healthcare workers (Swansea) and broader conditions of gender, income, and religion (KEMEA, Spain, MDI). Considerable diversity in target populations will ensure strong differences in research outcomes across cases, although all have an emphasis upon minority or at-risk communities during various stages of the COVID pandemic.

The fourth subcategory of COREQ Domain 2 pertains to how data was collected from interviews and surveys. All cases noted the use of an interview guide, with some (e.g., Swansea) even sharing the interview guide with participants. The use of a formal guide is common best practice and indicates that any interview feedback was conducted in a semi-structured manner. Repeat interviews were not commonly utilized within and across the case studies – the logistics of this, including the timing of the study as well as the difficulties maintaining contact with target populations are referenced causes (likewise, while some cases offered to send transcript notes to the participants, this was not a commonly referenced request or activity). Most case studies utilized audio/video recordings with the consent of participants, with many also taking field notes to supplement the recording. The duration of each interview/survey varied, from roughly twenty minutes to one hour. As such, it is likely that the quotes and responses between cases with relatively short interviews to those of an hour will differ in richness (however, longer interviews are more burdensome to the participant, and fewer individuals are likely able to participate).

Most cases generated raw data in the form of interviews, with some utilizing companion surveys. As such all cases will have quotations as raw data, which in COREQ Domain 3 will be coded, sorted, and analysed for common themes and perspectives.

2.5 Coordination Guidelines: Logistics and Administration

Coordinating interview teams in qualitative research studies is an important aspect of increasing the rigor, transparency, and generalizability of the findings. COREQ provides instructions regarding how multiple interview teams should be grounded and managed to derive generalizable output. COVINFORM followed these guidelines, including: develop roles and responsibilities for project teams, establish general protocols for interviewing, ensuring consistency in data collection, monitor data quality, and establish a common evaluation protocol. Ensuring consistency in data collection is also crucial. The interview team should use a standardized data collection protocol to ensure that the data collected is consistent across different interviewers. This includes using a standardized interview guide, and a protocol for handling missing data or non-response. The team should also continuously monitor the quality of the data collected, including the completeness and accuracy of the data.

One of the key steps is to develop clear roles and responsibilities among the interview team members, including who is responsible for recruiting participants, conducting interviews, transcribing, and translating data, and analysing data. This ensures that everyone is aware of their responsibilities and can work effectively. Via COREQ and syndemic theory, COVINFORM held regular all-case meetings and more targeted office hours to foster cross-case organization, address questions, and provide regular feedback.

Table 4. Case-studies baseline requirements: Logistics and Administration.

Other requirements and logistical considerations for case-studies coordination	
C. Each case shall be coordinated based logistical and administrative requirements (frequency of meetings, and transfer of data, files, and written materials)	
Meetings were held twice-monthly across all case study teams, with weekly ‘office hours’ granted to allow for a deeper dive into each interview project. Likewise, research timelines were established to ensure a completion of the project in 2023 – this includes (i) creating interview study, (ii) outlining interview subject criteria, (iii) interview protocols and analysis, and (iv) common analysis.	
C1. Regular meetings, at least quarterly, shall occur between COVINFORM coordinators and the principal investigators of each case.	
This was conducted – see above.	
C1a. Synthesized findings shall be shared on these meetings, identifying potentially shared/common outcomes and lessons learned that may serve as core project conclusions regarding pandemic response and recovery at varying levels of scale.	
This was conducted – see above.	
C2. Written and oral reports, including results and/or data, shall be made available in a manner consistent with law and scientific best practice.	
All interview teams completed COREQ assignment sheets that indicated study questions, progress, and themes. This is consistent with best practice for qualitative research.	
C2a. Publications, podcasts/webinars, conference presentations, posters, white papers, etc.	
In progress.	

COREQ Domain 3: Data Analytics and Reporting

Last of the three COREQ Domains, Domain 3 emphasizes the process by which collected raw data is coded, sorted, derived for output themes, and checked for quality control. Considerations include whether those sifting through raw data are adequately trained or potentially biased in identifying major and minor themes within interviews, as well as the process by which quotations or content/discourse analysis are presented as findings relative to the larger body of data.

Moreover, and as stated before, case coordination requirements may evolve over time. As such, a Thematic Block Script template was added to guide and help write the interviews’ scripts and later conduct data analysis and reporting by taking a systematic mixed approach: Bottom-up – code, classify, and analyse the data focusing on emerging themes from the participants’ interviews; and Top-down – check for themes related to the factors and indicators/variables selected in each case to characterize the socio-ecological system frame established in each case.

As primary data collection is still ongoing until February 2023, COREQ’s Domain 3 global analysis of inputs and outputs will be included in D3.8 upon case-studies data analysis and cross-comparison.

3 Conclusions

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a profound impact on communities around the world, with some communities (e.g., immigrant or minority populations) being disproportionately affected by social, economic, and other disruptions. Syndemic theory suggests that multiple health and social problems interact in ways that are additive or multiplicative, leading to worse outcomes than would occur if each problem were considered in isolation. Considering this, COVINFORM wanted to test the theory of syndemics by studying how minority populations have experienced disproportionate disruption from the COVID-19 pandemic – particularly using case studies across Europe to (a) gather unique and rich narratives of individual cities, while also (b) garnering common feedback for a pan-European experience.

To conduct this research, the team used COREQ (Consolidated Criteria for Reporting Qualitative Research) guidelines to ensure rigor and transparency in their study design, data collection, and analysis. They began by developing a research question consistent with syndemic theory, and later crafted inclusion and exclusion criteria to identify the specific minority populations that would be included in the study. They then used a criterion-based purposeful sampling strategy to select a diverse sample of participants that represented different minority populations.

The team then used multiple methods of data collection, including interviews, surveys, observations, and document analysis, to gather data from different sources. They also used a standardized data collection protocol to ensure consistency in the data collected across different interviewers. Transcription and translation of the data is still ongoing, and thematic analysis to identify the themes, patterns, and relationships that emerge from the data will be used through standardized method across all case studies.

The COVINFORM team was particularly interested in how vulnerable populations experienced disproportionate disruption from the COVID-19 pandemic, including poor access to healthcare, job loss, and increased stress and anxiety. Similar considerations include whether such populations suffered disproportionate job loss, if their cultural or social lives were particularly and permanently altered, whether household income and means dropped, and how the population interacted with the government regarding risk communication and other programs. Assessment of these questions, which is ongoing, will evaluate whether one or more cases experienced syndemic-level disruption, and may demonstrate how multiple health and social problems interacted in ways that were additive or multiplicative, leading to worse outcomes than would occur if each problem were considered in isolation.

The study's transparency and rigor were ensured by following COREQ guidelines, which provided a standardized format for reporting qualitative research, which allows other researchers to understand the context and limitations of the study, and to assess the generalizability of the findings. Emphasis is placed upon input rigor and interview protocol development – all cases developed criterion-based inclusion criteria, characterized purposeful sampling strategies to promote interview engagement, and tracked the qualifications and potential biases of those administering the interview (consistent with scientific best practices). This, along with the triangulation of outcomes and regular meetings with the entire COVINFORM team and via office hours, promotes internal and external validity. This study provides an example of how COREQ can be used to test syndemic theory in real-world situations, and how it can be used to understand the impact of the pandemic on minority populations.

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Appendix A. Process for case study set-up and implementation (figure presented in D3.3).

Appendix B. COREQ Table Requirements (Tong et al., 2007).

<i>Domain – Category – Item</i>	<i>Considerations</i>
Domain 1: Research team and reflexivity	
<i>Personal Characteristics</i>	
1. Interviewer/facilitator	Which author/s conducted the interview or focus group?
2. Credentials	What were the researcher's credentials?
3. Occupation	What was their occupation at the time of the study?
4. Gender	Was the researcher male or female?
5. Experience and training	What experience or training did the researcher have?
<i>Relationship with participants</i>	
6. Relationship established	Was a relationship established prior to study commencement?
7. Participant knowledge of the interviewer	What did the participants know about the researcher?
8. Interviewer characteristics	What characteristics were reported about the interviewer/facilitator?
Domain 2: study design	
<i>Theoretical framework</i>	
9. Methodological orientation and Theory	What methodological orientation was stated to underpin the study?
<i>Participant selection</i>	
10. Sampling	How were participants selected?
11. Method of approach	How were participants approached?
12. Sample size	How many participants were in the study?
13. Non-participation	How many people refused to participate or dropped out?
<i>Setting</i>	
14. Setting of data collection	Where was the data collected?
15. Presence of non-participants	Was anyone else present besides the participants and researchers?
16. Description of sample	What are the important characteristics of the sample?
<i>Data collection</i>	
17. Interview guide	Were questions, prompts, guides provided by the authors? Was it pilot tested?
18. Repeat interviews	Were repeat interviews carried out? If yes, how many?
19. Audio/visual recording	Did the research use audio or visual recording to collect the data?
20. Field notes	Were field notes made during and/or after the interview or focus group?
21. Duration	What was the duration of the interviews or focus group?
22. Data saturation	Was data saturation discussed?
23. Transcripts returned	Were transcripts returned to participants for comment and/or correction?
Domain 3: analysis and findings	
<i>Data analysis</i>	
24. Number of data coders	How many data coders coded the data?
25. Description of the coding tree	Did authors provide a description of the coding tree?

26. Derivation of themes	Were themes identified in advance or derived from the data?
27. Software	What software, if applicable, was used to manage the data?
28. Participant checking	Did participants provide feedback on the findings?
<i>Reporting</i>	
29. Quotations presented	Were participant quotations presented to illustrate the themes / findings?
30. Data and findings consistent	Was there consistency between the data presented and the findings?
31. Clarity of major themes	Were major themes clearly presented in the findings?
32. Clarity of minor themes	Is there a description of diverse cases or discussion of minor themes?

Appendix C1. Case-studies' COREQ Domain 1 Synthesis.

Domain 1: Research Team and Reflexivity					
Personal Characteristics	<i>Belgium_UANTWERPEN</i>	<i>Austria_SYNYO</i>	<i>Sweden_UGOT</i>	<i>UK_MDI</i>	<i>Wales_SU</i>
2. Credentials What were the researcher's credentials?	Bachelor in History and Politics, Master in International Development	PhD in Anthropology (VA, ND), Master's in communication science (DB)	3 Master students Professor 1 Ph.D. student 2 Journalist students The main selection criterion for all interviewers was previous experience of interviewing. The Master students and the Ph.D. student that conducted interviews were also well acquainted with central theories and literature in risk and crisis communication. The journalist students were at the time studying a course in journalism research and writing their Bachelor Thesis.	An international award-winning producer/director and media executive with a passion for social development. He was a senior executive at the BBC till 2007. He was awarded the Fellowship of the Royal Television Society in 2005, and the Fellowship of the Institute of Leadership and Development in 2011. He has worked as Media Expert for the Council of Europe and is a trustee for the Media Diversity Institute.	<i>PhD, 10 years of experience in qualitative interviewing of medicalised topics with people socially (not formally ethically) considered vulnerable in that context.</i>
3. Occupation What was their occupation at the time of the study?	Researcher	Post-doctoral researcher & project manager (VA, NDF), researcher & project coordinator (DB)	See above	Director of Media Empowered Social Innovation	<i>Postdoctoral researcher</i>
4. Gender Was the researcher male or female?	Woman	Woman	Women - 4 Men - 3	Man	Woman

<p>5. Experience and training What experience or training did the researcher have?</p>	<p>3 months qualitative research for Masters Thesis in Malawi refugee camp</p>	<p>All researchers are trained (qualitative) social scientists, though of different disciplines (anthropology, communication science).</p>	<p>All researchers and students had experience from interviewing. The Professor and Master Students had already conducted research interviews in previous research projects and/or when writing Bachelor and Master Thesis. For journalism students, interviewing is a very central part of their education and a skill they acquire and practice repeatedly during their training. The journalism students involved in the COVINFORM project are in their third semester.</p>	<p>Experienced journalist and media expert</p>	<p>PhD in Human Geography</p>
<p>Personal Characteristics</p>	<p><i>Greece_KEMEA</i></p>	<p><i>Spain_URJC</i></p>	<p><i>Portugal_FS</i></p>	<p><i>Germany_SINUS</i></p>	<p><i>Italy_SAPIENZA</i></p>
<p>2. Credentials What were the researcher's credentials?</p>	<p>Several members of the team have participated in EU projects such as COVINFORM, PERCEPTIONS, ERADICATING, MEDEA and IRIS. The team also holds degrees such as Masters in Crisis emergency disaster management, Multicultural education, Special education, International Security and Law, Arts, Geopolitics, Healthcare Management and Business Administration, Bachelor's in Primary Education, Philosophy, Psychology, Pedagogy, Law, Sociology and History and Ethnology. Additionally, expertise and a certified trainer in Health Emergency Management and Civil Protection, and several years of work experience with qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods</p>	<p>The team has experience in EU projects such as COVINFORM, PERCEPTIONS and JP-COOPS. Team composed of members who are Doctor's Assistant Professors, previous professors, researchers and pre-doctoral visiting researchers. Members also hold degrees such as PhD's, Master's in Applied Sociology to Social Problems, and degrees in Political Science and Sociology</p>	<p>Clinical psychologist (master's degree); Junior social psychologist (master's degree)</p>	<p>Recruiting: small civil society organisation (CSO) based in the Heidelberg area specialising in consulting and arranging support for vulnerable women. Interviewers: 1) PhD in political science; 2) MA in European studies. Analysis: PhD in sociology of music/culture, with a focus on mixed-methods data analysis.</p>	<p>PhD in Demography, PhD in Demography and Social Statistics (MHLV), PhD in Psychology (DC)</p>

	research, and project management at national and international level.				
3. Occupation What was their occupation at the time of the study?	Research Associates	Research Assistants - 2 Researchers and University Professors - 3	Researcher at FS; Project manager and principal researcher at FS	Recruiting: CSO director. Interviewing: 1) senior researcher; 2) researcher. Analysis: senior researcher.	Associate Professor (EA), Post-doctoral researcher (MHLV), Assistant Professor (DC)
4. Gender Was the researcher male or female?	Women – 3 Men - 2	Women – 2 Men - 3	2 Women	Recruiting: women-identifying. Interviewing: 1) women-identifying; 2) men-identifying. Analysis: men-identifying.	All three researchers identify as women.
5. Experience and training What experience or training did the researcher have?	The team holds degrees such as Masters in Crisis emergency disaster management, Multicultural education, Special education, International Security and Law, Arts, Geopolitics, Healthcare Management and Business Administration, Bachelor's in Primary Education, Philosophy, Psychology, Pedagogy, Law, Sociology and History and Ethnology. Additionally, expertise and a certified trainer in Health Emergency Management and Civil Protection, and several years of work experience with qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods research, and project management at national and international level.	Team members include lecturers in International Relations and Political Science and Public Management, in Political Science and Public Management and Economics/Journalism/Law degrees, in Criminology degree, in Equality and Gender degree, in Social Work degrees, in Strategic Management degree of Public Security and in Public Administration Master's, specialized in public administration, analysis and evaluation of public/welfare/urban policies and public opinion on public policies and services. Members also hold PhD's focused on political and electoral behavior, Master's on Democracy	Curricular training and approximately 15 interviews done previously for the same project; Curricular training, interviews conducted for previous research, and interviews conducted for the current project	Recruiting: over 20 years of field experience working with vulnerable women. Interviewing: 1) ca. 15 years experience working on public health projects with vulnerable populations; 2) ca. five years experience working on public health projects. Analysis: ca. 6 years working on European Commission-funded studies in fields related to sociology of culture.	All researchers are trained in qualitative methods, EA and DC have several years of experience of fieldwork using qualitative methods

		and Government, Political Science and International Cooperation, degrees in Law and Political Science and Administration, Postgraduate courses in Applied Social Research, and several years of experience working in qualitative research, national and international social project management, European projects, and consultancy for different national and foreign institutions, in matters related to governance and policy evaluation.			
Relationship with participants	<i>Belgium_UANTWERPEN</i>	<i>Austria_SYNYO</i>	<i>Sweden_UGOT</i>	<i>UK_MDI</i>	<i>Wales_SU</i>
6. Relationship established Was a relationship established prior to study commencement?	None	While our research has not yet been conducted due to the challenges described above, we do have a pre-existing relationship with one of the social supermarkets due to the recruiting of residents for interviews. As such, they were aware of the project and three of the researchers (VA, DB, RB).	No	The interviewer had some relationships established prior to the interviews.	Nurses: Briefly through email contact, although some participants had had a chat with Louise Condon, who has been a nurse: all were offered to have a chat with Louise or Diana. Healthcare managers: On some occasions, a prior connection had been established during a reading group and through gatekeepers Survey respondents: none

7. Participant knowledge of the interviewer What did the participants know about the researcher?	Researcher at the University of Antwerpen	We cannot answer this yet, but we will probably follow the procedure established for the resident interviews and provide the interlocutors with some information about the interviewers to ease them into the conversation and somewhat reduce the power imbalance.	Most of the participants of the case study were contacted through intermediaries, usually supervisors/contact persons of study circles, childcare centres, or homework help organisations. The supervisors very briefly introduced the project and the interviewees to the participants.	N/A	Interviews: Very little: role in the research, experience with the method, some knew some of my further research background beyond COVINFORM Survey respondents: nothing
8. Interviewer characteristics What characteristics were reported about the interviewer/facilitator?	I introduced myself as a research at the University, working on an EU-funded project looking at the impact of the pandemic on different groups in society	We will introduce ourselves, our position and our organisation, as well as the project and its objectives.	When meeting the interviewee (participant), the interviewer would present both the project and her-/himself more in detail (orally and by handing over a written presentation of the project).	Interviewer's professional credentials such as occupation, name, and experience	Interviews: My gender, my status as immigrant to Wales, having English as my second language, my education (specialism and doctorate achieved), employment as postdoctoral researcher on this project, and some of my personal pandemic experiences that relate to their experiences Survey respondents: nothing
Relationship with participants	<i>Greece_KEMEA</i>	<i>Spain_URJC</i>	<i>Portugal_FS</i>	<i>Germany_SINUS</i>	<i>Italy_SAPIENZA</i>
6. Relationship established Was a relationship established prior to study commencement?	No previous relationship was established.	No previous relationship was established.	No	No	The fieldwork has not started yet, however we have already contacted the interviewees during the quantitative survey. Therefore

					they know the objective of the case study and more generally of the COVINFORM project.
7. Participant knowledge of the interviewer What did the participants know about the researcher?	None. With the cooperation of third sector organizations (CSOs) and utilizing the network that has been established between KEMEA with third party entites, we have contacted migrant, refugee and members of the Roma community as well as Law Enforcement Agents. In both interview pools, thematic areas revolved around perceptions, trust and interaction with each target group in a pre-covid-19 and during-COVID-19 phase along with health related uncertainties, economic activity, administrative situation and household issues.	None. With the cooperation of third sector organizations (CSOs) that became our entry points, we have contacted migrant individuals for whom health related uncertainties mounted on top of race, economic activity, access to social benefits, administrative situation and household issues.	Name, gender, and qualifications	No	Background, credentials, work position.
8. Interviewer characteristics What characteristics were reported about the interviewer/facilitator?	They introduced themselves as professionals who were conducting a European comparative research across different countries within the pandemic context.	They introduced themselves as professionals who were conducting a European compared research across different countries within the pandemic context.	Condition of low vision.	They introduced themselves as professionals who were conducting a European compared research across different countries within the pandemic context.	We will introduce ourselves, our position and our organisation, as well as the project and its objectives.

Appendix C2. Case-studies' COREQ Domain 2 Synthesis.

Domain 2: Study Design					
Theoretical framework	<i>Belgium_UANTWERPEN</i>	<i>Austria_SYNYO</i>	<i>Sweden_UGOT</i>	<i>UK_MDI</i>	<i>Wales_SU</i>
9. Methodological orientation and Theory What methodological orientation was stated to underpin the study?		Besides complex systems theory and intersectionality, the case study is theoretically grounded in embodiment (e.g. Csordas 1990), particularly focusing on the embodied experience of risk.	The case study departs from theory of sensemaking in analysing information seeking and communicative behaviour within a social constructivist framework, i.e., in recognition of the embeddedness of individual behaviour and the dialectic of agency and structure. The study has a comparative approach; data from Sweden and Germany are compared and analysed.	Ethnography, document analysis	Interviews: Phenomenology, discourse analysis Art workshop: Phenomenology, discourse analysis Survey: discourse analysis, content analysis
Theoretical framework	<i>Greece_KEMEA</i>	<i>Spain_URJC</i>	<i>Portugal_FS</i>	<i>Germany_SINUS</i>	<i>Italy_SAPIENZA</i>
9. Methodological orientation and Theory What methodological orientation was stated to underpin the study?	The questionnaire and the data collection techniques for the interviews consider the research questions and, therefore, the theoretical-conceptual framework of this research, specifically socio-economical systems framework, emphasized in perceptions and trust. The analysis and processing of the data collected will also be carried out using methodological tools such as Discourse analysis and content	The questionnaire and the data collection techniques for the interviews consider the research questions and, therefore, the theoretical-conceptual framework of this research, specifically socio-ecological systems framework. The analysis and processing of the data collected will also be carried out using methodological tools such as Discourse analysis and content analysis.	Socio-ecological systems as theoretical and methodological framework; Thematic analysis to address data analysis through a mixed approach: Bottom-up and top-down	The questionnaire and the data collection techniques for the interviews consider the research questions and, therefore, the theoretical-conceptual framework of this research, specifically socio-ecological systems framework. The analysis and processing of the data collected will also be carried out using methodological tools such as Discourse analysis and content analysis.	Ethnography, content analysis, anthropological demography, psychology.

	analysis. We also take into consideration the ethnographical methodological elements due to our target groups' characteristics.				
Participant selection	Belgium_UANTWERPEN	Austria_SYNYO	Sweden_UGOT	UK_MDI	Wales_SU
10. Sampling How were participants selected? e.g. purposive, convenience, consecutive, snowball	Recruited through organisations or actors working with migrants in Borgerhout/Antwerpen Noord. And then through Snowball sampling	Store manager will suggest us whom to interview from their employees. As the supermarkets are rather small we expect to interview the majority of employees in each of the three social supermarkets we will choose as field sites.	All participants were selected from ethnical minority groups living primarily in one specific migrant dense suburb in the outskirts of Gothenburg, Hjällbo. A snowball recruitment approach was used. Only individual interviews were conducted, with one exception when two participants were interviewed at the same time. No focus group interviews were conducted.	Purposive	Interviews and art workshops: Purposive sampling via a set of eligibility criteria and distributed via a professional network. Also snowball sampling. Survey: purposive and convenience sampling
11. Method of approach How were participants approached? e.g. face-to-face, telephone, mail, email	Some participants were contacted through personal contacts - so via-via through text or email. The rest were contacted face-to-face in walk-in moments at organisations providing assistance.	In the first step, we approached the supermarket management via telephone (or, in the case of the supermarket where we recruited women for resident interviews, face-to-face). Due to the workload before the holidays, we will arrange the interviews in January. Interviews are planned to take place in face-to-face settings.	The participants were usually contacted face-to-face by an intermediary, usually a person in charge of some form of interest organization/group operating within the geographically defined recruitment area (see also form field no 7). All interviews were conducted face-to-face.	Telephone, email	Interviews and art workshop: Via email and face-to-face at events and at the hospital (Louise) Survey: via organisations, personal networks of a collaborator, and in person at shops the sample population was known to frequent
12. Sample size How many participants were in the study?	Approximate sample sizes: Key informant/expert interviews: n IS. Conducted 13 so far. Interviews with migrants living in Borgerhout and Antwerpen	For the case study with SPAR AG we aimed for a sample size of Women working in the supermarket: 12-16 Management: 3-6 These numbers might need adjustment depending on the	The established number of interviews was 12, 6 women and 6 men living in the two pre-defined areas. However, all in all 15 interviews were conducted since three were of rather pure quality, due mainly to language	The plan was to conduct around 20 interviews, but we did 31 interviews in total.	174 in the questionnaire (complete) 16 for the interviews (planned: partially achieved) 8-12 for the art workshops (planned)

	Noord: n 20/25. Conducted 17 so far.	size of the social supermarkets and women employed.	issues, and will not be included in the sample.		
13. Non-participation How many people refused to participate or dropped out?	Difficult to measure the rates of non-participation, as migrants were mostly approached face to face.	N/A	n/a	Two people dropped out because they could not make the proposed time and place.	Interviews: 1 so far Survey respondents: impossible to say
Participant selection	<i>Greece_KEMEA</i>	<i>Spain_URJC</i>	<i>Portugal_FS</i>	<i>Germany_SINUS</i>	<i>Italy_SAPIENZA</i>
10. Sampling How were participants selected? e.g. purposive, convenience, consecutive, snowball	Purposive sample combined with snowballing.	Purposive sample combined with snowballing.	Purposive and convenience sample. Extensive list of contacts from statal websites and private websites. Visits to close by LTCFs upon conducting field work at the site.	Purposive sample combined with snowballing.	Snowball
11. Method of approach How were participants approached? e.g. face-to-face, telephone, mail, email	Face-to-face, Telephone and email	Email, face-to-face and telephone.	Via email and telephone to reach out, explain project and arrange for time to interview participants; Most were approached in person once at the site due to lack of response in previous method. All interviews were conducted face-to-face		Email, face-to-face
12. Sample size How many participants were in the study?	How many participants were in the study? - 5 Law Enforcement Agents - 5 individuals with the following characteristics: members of the Roma community and/or Refugees	13 migrants. The sample is composed of thirteen respondents from the two largest migrant communities in Madrid, that is, the Latin American community and the Moroccan community, and is divided into	Total interviews conducted: 43 (34 women); Total participating LTCFs: 13 LTCF administration: 11 (10 women) LTCF workers: 12 (10 women)	Civil society organisation representatives: N=5. Public health practitioners: N=5. N=6 low-SES women without migration background.	We plan to interview 14 people

	<p>and/or Migrants and/or representatives of the aforementioned target groups.</p> <p>In addition, interviews were conducted with institutional actors to get a better understanding of the system:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -5 policy makers with responsibilities associated with health, governance, social services, family, social data management, etc. -5 practitioners connected to several WP's project domains: public health, institutional communication, governance...etc. -5 CSO representatives working with the general population and minorities, vulnerable and/or migrant/refugee populations. -12 Low SES (socio-economic status) women. <p>All interviews have already been conducted.</p> <p>Interviews to be conducted:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 5 Communication experts and policy makers in relation to communication campaigns and strategy for COVID-19. 	<p>nine (69%) Latin American respondents and four (31%) Moroccan respondents. In terms of gender, of the thirteen interviewees, eight are women (62%) and five are men (38%).</p> <p>In addition, interviews were conducted with institutional actors to get a better understanding of the system:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -4 policy makers with responsibilities associated with health, social services, family, social data management, etc. -5 practitioners connected to several WP's project domains: public health, institutional communication, governance...etc. -5 CSOs working with vulnerable and/or migrant populations. <p>All interviews have already been conducted.</p>	<p>LTCF elderly residents: 20 (14 women)</p>	<p>N=8 low-SES women with migration background. N=4 low-SES men with migration background (will recruit N=2 more)</p>	
<p>13. Non-participation How many people refused to participate or dropped out?</p>	<p>We did not find any systematic patterns of non-response. Response rates finally distribute as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For resident respondents, (12 low socio-economic women) response/participation rate of 100%. - For Decision-makers 	<p>For resident respondents, seventeen people were contacted to participate in the interviews (ten from Latin America (59%) and seven from Morocco (41%), in line with the representation of these communities in Madrid). Thirteen people finally responded and</p>	<p>Total LTCFs contacted (phone, email and in-person): around 45. Total LTCFs contacted via phone and email: around 28. Total LTCFs contacted in-person: around 17. Once at the institution, after acceptance of participation from LTCFs administration, no</p>	<p>We did not find any systematic patterns of non-response. Exact response rates will be reported in a forthcoming iteration of the COREQ.</p>	<p>-</p>

	<p>respondents, the response rate reached 100%.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For Practitioners, the response rate was 100%. - For CSOs, the response rate reached 100%. - For Roma and LEAs, the response rate reached 100%. 	<p>participated (of which nine respondents are from Latin America (69%) and four are from Morocco (31%)), giving a response/participation rate of 76%.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For Decision-makers respondents, the response rate reached 80%. - For Practitioners, the response rate was 100%. - For CSOs, the response rate reached 71%. 	<p>participant (worker, elderly, administration) refused to participate or dropped out.</p>		
Setting	<i>Belgium_UANTWERPEN</i>	<i>Austria_SYNYO</i>	<i>Sweden_UGOT</i>	<i>UK_MDI</i>	<i>Wales_SU</i>
14. Setting of data collection Where was the data collected?	<p>At various organisations 'walk-in' moments, for example SAAMO De Wijk, Elegast. Or in cafes when participants were recruited through snowball sampling. Interviews with experts were mostly conducted at their work space or online.</p>	<p>Data will be collected in the supermarkets (observation) as well as in locations chosen by the interlocutors (e.g., coffee houses).</p>	<p>All interviews were conducted in the area where the interviewees lived, in the premises made available by the organization that mediated the recruitment. No interview was conducted in the interviewee's home. All interviews were conducted in separate rooms or in separate parts of a large room, in most cases with two interviewers present, one responsible for following the interview guidelines, and one responsible for relevant ad-hoc follow-up questions. In some cases, two people were interviewed at the same time.</p>	N/A	<p>Online (interviews and survey) and at the university (art workshop)</p>
15. Presence of non-participants Was anyone else present besides the participants and researchers?	<p>Sometimes workers from the organisation or community health workers would help with translation.</p>	N/A	<p>When the interview was conducted in a separate space of a large room, other people may have been present. However none close enough to interfere with/overhear the interview.</p>	<p>The only people present in the interviews were the interviewer and the cameraman, Bhasker Solanki. In one of the interviews, the interviewee came with her mother.</p>	No

			Also, in some cases a translator was present.		
16. Description of sample What are the important characteristics of the sample?	<p>The population that is the primary focus of our case study are members of migrant communities in Borgerhout and Antwerpen Noord, specifically migrants that arrived in Belgium more than 5 years ago.</p> <p>In addition to our target population, we will engage with three additional groups of participants, linked to work packages 4, 5 and 6:</p> <p>WP4 link: representatives from local-level government and decision makers (Stad Antwerpen)</p> <p>WPS link: professionals working in (mental) health services: GPs, psychologists, psychiatrists, councillors, etc.</p> <p>WP6 link: representatives from community-level initiatives and services (e.g. Coronababbels, Atlas vzw, De Borgerhoutse hulplijn)</p>	Women working at the frontline in social supermarket. We aim for a diverse sample in terms of migration background and age.	<p>The sample consists of persons that have migrated to Sweden, some early in life when they were infants, other later as adults. Knowledge of the Swedish language varied a lot, some of the interviewees spoke it fluently why others had difficulties in understanding and making themselves understood. Interviews were mainly conducted in Swedish, but also in English if needed.</p>	Gender, religion, ethnicity, age and community role	<p>Nurses: BAME background, qualified as nurse overseas, having worked in a Swansea hospital during the pandemic, mostly since January 2019</p> <p>Healthcare managers: White or BAME background, in senior positions in clinical and social care settings in Swansea, having worked in these settings in Swansea during the pandemic, mostly since January 2019</p> <p>Survey respondents: BAME background, living in Swansea, Neath, or Port Talbot</p>
Setting	<i>Greece_KEMEA</i>	<i>Spain_URJC</i>	<i>Portugal_FS</i>	<i>Germany_SINUS</i>	<i>Italy_SAPIENZA</i>
14. Setting of data collection Where was the data collected?	We contacted the aforementioned target groups as potential interviewees, and those who finally agreed were generally interviewed (on-site) in meeting rooms of CSOs, the HQ of KEMEA, or exceptionally	Through the CSOs that became our entry points, we contacted migrant individuals as potential interviewees, and those who finally agreed were generally interviewed in meeting rooms of these CSOs or exceptionally in	City of Évora in the Alentejo Region of Portugal.	Municipality of Mannheim, Germany.	Data will be collected at the hospital where HCWs work

	<p>in cafés in the neighbourhoods where the interviewees lived. The familiarity of these spaces for the interviewees facilitated their trust and openness to talk. Remote interviews were conducted by utilizing platforms such as Skype, Microsoft teams, Webex and Zoom. All interviews were conducted in Greece.</p>	<p>cafés in the neighbourhoods where the interviewees lived. The familiarity of these spaces for the interviewees facilitated their trust and openness to talk. All interviews were conducted in the city of Madrid.</p>			
15. Presence of non-participants Was anyone else present besides the participants and researchers?	None of the interviewees were accompanied during the interviews.	None	Sometimes, there was no other space to conduct the interview besides the room the elderly was on, so there were other LTCFs residents in the same room, but with no capacity to understand due to degenerated abilities.	None	-
16. Description of sample What are the important characteristics of the sample?	<p>For the citizen sample (low ses women), main selection criteria were nationality of origin, length of stay in the country (more than 5 years), gender, income, social status and educational level.</p> <p>For the interviews with institutional actors (Policy and Decision makers in governmental and healthcare sectors), we reached out to the heads of each institution whereas the main criteria was their employment activity, role and affiliation with the relevant policies, decisions implemented towards COVID-19.</p> <p>For the interviews of the case study (Minority groups and LEAs), the main characteristics were origin, employment, role,</p>	<p>For the citizen sample, main selection criteria were nationality of origin, length of stay in the country (more than 5 years), gender, and income. For the interviews with institutional actors, we reached out to the heads of each institution (City Hall and its services, namely social services, policy, firefighters, etc.).</p>	<p>Elderly residents in long-term care facilities, as well as LTCFs' workers who provide for elderly on a daily basis and administration staff who are decision-makers regarding their LTCF.</p>	<p>Inclusion criteria were: 1) gender, as determined via self-identification; 2) low socioeconomic status, as determined by receipt of social assistance; 3) for some respondents, migration background, defined as at least one parent having been born outside Germany.</p>	

	frequency and interaction with other relevant groups, socio-demographic status.				
Data collection	<i>Belgium_UANTWERPEN</i>	<i>Austria_SYNYO</i>	<i>Sweden_UGOT</i>	<i>UK_MDI</i>	<i>Wales_SU</i>
17. Interview guide Were questions, prompts, guides provided by the authors? Was it pilot tested?	<p>The interview guide included questions to guide the interviews, as well as prompts during the interview. It was not pilot tested, but after a few interviews with migrants we realized that language barriers meant some of the questions were not properly understood. Also, we received feedback from migrants interviewed at the beginning that the questions were too specialist/technical, and a bit too abstract (there was too much of a focus on specific psychological symptoms as if they were being questioned by a doctor, rather than their experiences during the pandemic). So we adapted the interview guide after this.</p>	<p>We prepared an interview questionnaire with a set of questions to guide us through the interviews. This guide has to be adapted to the new location, i.e. the social supermarket. Once finalised, the guide will be pilot tested to make sure it is understandable.</p>	<p>An interview guide was provided by SINUS and UGOT in collaboration with other partners in the project. The guide was thoroughly elaborated, and several adjustments were made. The first interview set out to be a pilot, but since the guide worked well the interview was included in the sample.</p>	<p>Yes, questions we refined by members of research team</p>	<p>Provided to interview participants on request. The list of questions was not pilot tested.</p>
18. Repeat interviews Were repeat interviews carried out? If yes, how many?	None	None	None	None	no

19. Audio/visual recording Did the research use audio or visual recording to collect the data?	Yes, my phone was used to record the interview, or Teams if interview took place online.	We are planning to audio-record the interviews and to collect drawings of those spaces in which the women felt in-/secure.	Yes, with consent	Every interview was video recorded	Audio recording of the interviews and visual for the art works
20. Field notes Were field notes made during and/or after the interview or focus group?	None	We are planning to write field notes of all research activities by all participating researchers.	Yes	Yes.	Yes, at art workshop
21. Duration What was the duration of the interviews or focus group?	30 minutes to 1 hour	1 hour	18 to 44 minutes	Approximately 1 hour	Interviews: an hour Art workshop: 2 hours
22. Data saturation Was data saturation discussed?	Not yet	Our approach is explorative, as our literature review has clearly demonstrated that frontline-workers in the supermarket are an underresearched population. As such, we want to gain an in-depth understanding of the women in a specific context – the social supermarket of the Arbeiter-Samariter-Bund – and explore it through our analysis. The number of supermarket employees at the social supermarkets are limited, as such, we only aim at explorative research rather than theoretical saturation.	None	Not yet	Not with participants. Yes amongst researchers

23. Were transcripts returned to participants for comment and/or correction?	No	No	None	The interviewees were not interested to read the transcript. They are interested in the short videos and MDI will be sent those back to them.	No (omission of remarks offered before commencing with the interview)
Data collection	Greece_KEMEA	Spain_URJC	Portugal_FS	Germany_SINUS	Italy_SAPIENZA
17. Interview guide Were questions, prompts, guides provided by the authors? Was it pilot tested?	Interview guides were designed including research questions to guide the interviews. Different guides were used for interviews with each target group. Each guide contains a beginning section with a brief explanation of the project to be provided to the interviewee prior to the interview, without going into details so as to not bias their answers. Official consent forms and project's info sheets were also administered. Interviews were GDPR compliant and abided to all national and European legal framework ethical considerations, particularly in relation to conducting empirical research.	Interview guides were designed including questions to guide the interviews. Different guides were used for interviews with citizens and institutional actors. Each guide contains a beginning section with a brief explanation of the project to be provided to the interviewee prior to the interview, without going into details so as to not bias their answers. Official consent forms and project's info sheets were also administered.	The scripts were carefully elaborated given the goals, research questions, and indicators previously established. The first interviews of administration and worker target groups were considered pilots and included in the sample given their success. Upon the first interview of elderly, adjustments had to be made as they were not able to answer some questions designed with rating-scales. The script ended up being less structured than planned, but after adjustments were made, it worked out well	Interview guides were designed including questions to guide the interviews. Different guides were used for interviews with citizens and institutional actors. Each guide contains a beginning section with a brief explanation of the project to be provided to the interviewee prior to the interview, without going into details so as to not bias their answers. Official consent forms and project's info sheets were also administered.	Yes, questions we refined by members of research team
18. Repeat interviews Were repeat interviews carried out? If yes, how many?	No	None.	No	None	None

19. Audio/visual recording Did the research use audio or visual recording to collect the data?	Audio devices: mobile, tape recorder, recording software provided by meeting platforms (webex, microsoft teams, skype and zoom).	Audio devices: mobile, tape recorder	Audio. Participants consented to this, given that their audio would be erased after successful transcription.	Audio devices: mobile, tape recorder, recording software provided by meeting platforms (webex, microsoft teams, skype and zoom).	Yes video and audio recorded
20. Field notes Were field notes made during and/or after the interview or focus group?	Interviews were carried out by at least two interviewers so that one carried out the interviews and another one took notes and recorded the session.	Interviews were carried out by two interviewers so that one carried out the interviews and another one took notes and recorded the session.	Regarding the space, amenities, and observed relationship between staff and elderly available to elderly.	Field notes were made by the interviewer upon consent by the interviewee.	Yes
21. Duration What was the duration of the interviews or focus group?	40 minutes to 1 hour	Around 30-90 minutes.	LTCF administration: between 40min-1h LTCF workers: between 30-45min LTCF elderly residents: between 15-30min	40 minutes to 1 hour	Approximately 40 minutes
22. Data saturation Was data saturation discussed?	Yes	Yes.	We planned for at least: 1 private LTCF; 1 public LTCF; 1 third sector LTCF; 2 elderly from each LTCF type (both genders); 1 worker from each LTCF type; 1 admin from each LTCF type = minimum acceptable: 12 interviews.	Yes	Not yet
23. Were transcripts returned to participants for comment and/or correction?	Interviewees were given the opportunity to access them if they wanted to.	We gave them the opportunity to access them if they want to.	No. It was not planned, and no participant asked for this.	Interviewees were offered the opportunity to access their data, however, no interviewees have chosen to do so as of the time of reporting.	No

Appendix D. Updated timetable for setting up and execute COVINFORM case studies.

Date	Activity	Output	Partners engaged
August 2021	COVINFORM partners will provide inputs to add on the COREQ Requirements discussed in Tong et al (2007) (provided as the Table 1 of the present document) (e.g. information based on cross-cutting ethical issues presented on COVINFORM ethical report to be included...)	Updated of COREQ Requirements Discussed in Tong et al (2007)	All partners provide input until 22 August. Final systematization to be performed by FS until 31 August
August 2021	Literature review. Based on the identification of secondary sources for the case studies analysis, that can support contextualization and eventual generalization of future results, case studies leaders will finish the development of a background section based on literature review: describe study setting and population, including some reflections on what we already know about COVID-19 impact and response in this setting. Reviewing the case-study description (template provided on D3.1), including refining the research questions and contributions to COVINFORM goals, including review of overarching objectives and specific research questions considering both the context provided and other case-studies focusing on similar populations	Case-studies description update (case-studies description version .02) - 1) literature review providing the general context; and 2) update of the case studies description using the template provided in D3.1.	Case-studies' leaders
August 2021	Development of a structure for each case-studies' report	Case studies' report draft template	FS (WP3 leader)
early September 2021	Filling in the updated COREQ Requirements Discussed in Tong et al (2007) (output listed on the first line of this table), providing a GANT chart for the case-studies implementation	Reviewed description, COREQ and GANT chart for each case-study	Case-studies' leaders
early September 2021	Finalize distilling case study research questions and variables and identify commonalities between case-studies	Document for discussion	FS (WP3 leader)
September 2021	Reflections on commonalities/potential for collaboration with other case studies: 3 case-studies meetings, concerning each one of the case-studies clusters (target populations focused by the case-studies) to discuss the communalities document and agree on common variables to be addressed, research methodologies and timelines	List of common variables, common research methodology and research timelines to be implemented by the case-studies within each cluster	FS (WP3 leader) and case-studies' leaders
early October 2021	TRI will identify tools to assess and report on common variables. A meeting will be held in early October to discuss and select data collection methods and instruments to be used in each case-studies' cluster.	List of common variables to be addressed and tools to be used by the case-studies within each cluster regarding assessment and reporting of variables	TRI (WP2 leader) FS (WP3 leader) and case-studies' leaders

early November 2022	Meeting within case-studies' clusters to confirm the date of each case-study kick off and make sure data gathering has started; and to discuss the case studies' report draft template	1) List the kick off date of each case-study; 2) update the case-studies' report template (presented in August) in line with partners' feedback	FS (WP3 leader) and case-studies' leaders
October 2021 – March 2022	Gather case-studies baseline information. Each case-study leader will share secondary data gathered with FS (WP3 leader) by end February 2022, that will develop D3.4 – part 1.	First case-studies' report provided for each 10 case-studies (February 2022) D3.4 – case studies comparative report – part 1 (April 2022)	Case-studies' leaders and FS (WP3 leader)
March 2022 – onwards	Continue case-studies implementation and regular meetings to discuss cases status with each partner	Case-studies cluster meeting in Vienna monitor to monitor status and assess the need for case-studies adjustments	FS (WP3 leader), Case-studies' leaders, TRI
June 2022 – September 2022	Final case-study update and multi-site research design and methodological framework update. All case studies interview scripts finalisation (field work until February 2023)	Following Consortium meeting in Lisbon (May) Deliver D3.5 (September) and D3.6	Case-studies' leaders and FS (WP3 leader)
October 2022	Case-studies cluster meeting to monitor case-studies implementation and changes. Disseminate preliminary results from FS and UANTWERPEN case studies	Consortium meeting in Athens - Defined data analysis and reporting and WP3 templates sharing	FS (WP3 leader) and case-studies' leaders
November 2022 – January 2023	COREQ requirements filled in (domains 1 and 2) and submitted for D3.7	Deliver D3.7 - Case study coordination guidelines update (January)	FS (WP3 leader) and case-studies' leaders
end of February 2023	End of field work. Start of data analysis and reporting	Submission of socio-demographic data	FS (WP3 leader) and case-studies' leaders
early March 2023 - May 2023	Case studies data analysis and reporting – regular meetings.	Submission of data analysis and reporting	FS (WP3 leader) and case-studies' leaders
May 2023 - July 2023	Case studies data analysis and reporting – regular meetings. Systematize findings and comparisons. Identify guidelines and best practices	Cases studies analysis and reporting for D3.8 - Final case studies and comparative report	FS (WP3 leader) and case-studies' leaders